

Chemical Examination of the Stem of *Cassia alata*, Linn.

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In view of the importance in the indigenous system of medicine¹ and previous reports on various parts of the plant², we undertook a systematic chemical investigation of the stem of *Cassia alata*, Linn.³ (Fam. : Leguminosae). The present communication reports the isolation of a rare anthraquinone, 1,5-dihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone and 5-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone-1-*O*-rutinoside and β -sitosterol.

The air-dried and crushed defatted stem (8 kg; collected from the Botanical Garden, Bodh Gaya) was extracted with hot methanol and concentrated under reduced pressure. The alcoholic concentrate was resolved into water-soluble and water-insoluble parts.

The concentrated ethyl acetate extract of the water-soluble part was chromatographed over silica gel using C₆H₆-EtOAc gradient as eluent. Elution of the column with C₆H₆-EtOAc (8 : 2, v/v) furnished a compound which was crystallised from EtOAc-petroleum ether mixture as light yellow crystals (250 mg), m.p. 115° (Found : C, 56.70; H, 5.10. C₂₇H₃₀O₁₃ calcd. for : C, 57.65; H, 5.33%); responded colour reaction of anthraquinone⁴ and positive Molisch's test; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 255, 266, 288, 425 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 420 (OH), 1 675 (unchelated C=O), 1 630 (chelated C=O), 1 570, 1 450, 1 375, 1 270, 1 160, 900, 840, 730 cm⁻¹; pmr δ (300 MHz; CDCl₃) 0.90 (br, rhamnose methyl), 2.35 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.20-3.75 (br, sugar protons), 4.96 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C-1'' rhamnosyl), 5.20 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C-1' glucosyl), 7.55 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C-3) 7.62 (1H, dd, *J*

8 and 1.8 Hz, C-6), 7.66 (1H, t, *J* 8 Hz, C-7), 7.85 (1H, dd, *J* 8 and 1.8 Hz, C-8), 8.18 (1H, d, *J* 8 Hz, C-4), 12.60 (s, OH). Acid hydrolysis gave an aglycone, m.p. 195-97°, which was identified as 1,5-dihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone by uv, pmr and by direct comparison with an authentic sample⁵ and rhamnose and glucose (co-tlc and co-pc) in the hydrolysate. Acid hydrolysis of the methylated glycoside yielded a compound, m.p. 189-91°, which was identified as 1-hydroxy-5-methoxy-2-methylanthraquinone by comparison with an authentic sample⁵. This indicated the attachment of sugar moiety in position-1 of the aglycone. Identification of the degraded partially methylated sugars⁶ and the pmr spectrum of the glycoside (0.90 ppm)⁷ established the inter-sugar linkage between rhamnose and glucose in the form of rutinoside. Thus, above data led to the characterisation of compound as 5-hydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone-1-*O*-rutinoside.

The water-insoluble part was dissolved in minimum quantity of MeOH and chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol-C₆H₆ (8 : 2) eluate gave β -sitosterol. The C₆H₆-EtOAc (7 : 3) eluate gave a rare anthraquinone, m.p. 195-97°, which was identified as 1,5-dihydroxy-2-methylanthraquinone by its spectral data and direct comparison with an authentic sample⁵. Incidentally, the rare anthraquinone and its rutinoside are the first report of their occurrence from genus *Cassia*.

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